

Skin cancer or not? What patients should now about skin lesions and their clinical management.

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Abstract

In the case of a suspicious mole on the skin, the question always arises as to whether it is benign or malignant. Is it a harmless mole, a capillary malformation or a basal cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma or even a melanoma? Often the nevus can be assessed just by a close examination of the lesion and a few questions about its origin. However, every dermatologist knows all too well the problem that very different lesions can look extremely similar to the naked eye and even on dermatoscopy. Therefore, the question arises: how should dermatology deal with and communicate in such cases? This article identifies ways forward in this difficult situation, which occurs tens of thousands of times a day around the globe.

Rule one: keep it simple

What would medicine be without all the great Latin words and constantly new types and subtypes and sub-subtypes being discovered? It's great for science because the research results get better. But for frontline physicians, it's not quite optimal, because our patients are no medical researchers, at least not 99.9% of them.

So we have to keep in mind what our goal is in studying skin lesions: to make sure our patients don't die of skin cancer. It's that simple and that important. The best ally we have in this endeavor is the patients themselves. So we need to find a way to communicate with them in a way that they truly understand; and we shouldn't be afraid to forget our beloved Latin for a moment and talk to people as people. With all these different names for certain types of skin lesions, we somehow have forgotten something very important. Namely, explaining to patients that the following simple facts are important:^{1-7,11,12}

- There is non-melanocytic "white" skin cancer, which ranges from "slow growing, not very dangerous" (basal cell carcinoma) to "slow growing, but potentially life-threatening if treated too late" (squamous cell carcinoma).
- Dark skin cancers (malignant melanoma, lentigo maligna etc) progress from rather fast to incredibly rapid, behave aggressively, and are extremely deadly if not detected at a very early stage. Time is of utmost importance in these cases.
- Several other very rare skin cancers, which are also usually not brown or black in color, can occur from time to time.
- Precancerous lesions are tricky to diagnose, but to be taken very seriously.
- Cancerous skin tumors can develop in a seemingly harmless mole. However, skin cancer cells very often also develop from completely normal skin; it is a very dangerous misconception that skin cancer could only develop in a pre-existing nevus. As a patient, one should be alert when a new mole appears or an existing one suddenly begins to change, for example, when it becomes larger or thicker, changes color (not just to black), or when it develops symptoms such as a more or less constant itching, bleeding.
- Inborn moles (some congenital nevi) have an inherent risk of becoming cancerous. Even slightly more common than in acquired dysplastic nevi.
- Dysplastic nevi are by no means nevi that are on a direct path to malignancy, as was long believed. They are an entity in their own right. In contrast, melanocytic congenital "moles" are apparently associated with an increased risk of becoming cancerous.
- Completely benign (harmless) lesions can mimic features of the most common skin cancers (for example, the ubiquitous seborrheic keratosis).

This very basic knowledge should be taught to patients. It is the physician's duty to know the details. For patients, the above facts are sufficient. Especially the last point is crucial, because a dermatologist should always be straightforward and admit that in some cases only a pathologist is able to make a definite diagnosis after very detailed examination of the cells. This point is immensely important because diagnoses made with the naked eye are only 40% to 95% reliable, depending on the case and the experience of the physician (most mistakes happen in primary care settings). This is an

incredibly wide window. With dermatoscopy, old-fashioned with reflected light or digital, we are at 80% to 95%. Structure enhancing tools, used mainly in tele-medicine, makes outcomes possible which are similarly reliable as in dermatoscopy if the photo provided to the dermatologist is of excellent quality and the dermatologist himself, too. Results of about 99.8% are only possible for a pathologist. Many dermatologists have a habit of forgetting these numbers. Now artificial intelligence (A.I.) is just entering the scene and is giving amazingly good results, at least if the technology is fed good data (not necessarily the standard) and if patients get the photos right, which is a big problem. Even the best A.I. machine can't give an accurate result if the photos are blurry or if patients take a photo of their whole face when they want to know what the three millimeter lesion on their nose is. All this should be made known to the patients as transparency may increase compliance.¹³⁻²¹

Rule two: Don't scare your patient

Many dermatologists speak about excisional biopsies as if they were heart transplants or rocket science. The reason for this behavior remains unknown, but dramatizing what is just a ridiculously simple, quick and small procedure only scares the hell out of patients, resulting in massively compromised treatment acceptance.

To say it once and for all: biopsies are minimal medical interventions with a risk close to zero. On the other hand, a skin lesion that looks suspicious is usually actually risky. There is no justification whatsoever for not removing a suspicious skin area and letting a pathologist do his job. There is no reason to delay a biopsy, none.

When an existing nevus turns into a melanoma, it happens so quickly that there is no excuse for not having the scalpel ready at all times. Whatever is not definitely identifiable to the naked eye as a benign mole, stable and without abnormalities, must be removed. And it must be done immediately, not at some time in the future. Such a delay, which is the reality in many health systems, is completely inexcusable.

Rule three: remove it, no matter how

When it comes to excisional biopsies, there are several techniques and sub-techniques. In this article, we will definitely not continue the decades-old medical war between doctors of different nations. In the US, shave biopsies are standard in low-risk cases; in parts of Europe, a mildly dysplastic-looking nevus is already excised as if it were military surgery for the removal of a shrapnel.

Again, the issue is not properly addressed. The task is to remove the lesion in toto (completely in every direction), in sano (all tissue around the excised growth must be healthy skin or subcutaneous tissue), and in such a way that the pathologist can work with the material. How a dermatologist achieves these goals is completely irrelevant.

The same is true for follow-up. Most excisions up to 4 millimeters do not require surgical suturing. A bleeding-stopping substance at the end of the excision is usually sufficient, and the wound does not need any special care. Nevertheless, many frontline physicians seem obsessed with using their needles and closing small wounds with an astonishing number of stitches. However, this is only justified in patients who explicitly request to avoid a readily visible scar and in those with wound healing disorders; and even in these, one should think twice about which wound management is the easiest and safest. In most others, biopsy wounds should not be closed until they are 5 millimeters or larger. For smaller ones, suturing the wound only steals patient time and nerves; worse, it decreases acceptance for rapid biopsies. Below 5 millimeters, the motto should be: in toto, in sano, bleeding stopper, band-aid and you're done.²⁻⁹

Rule four: Follow a minimalist algorithm.

Sometimes less is more. This is even more true in the case discussed here. That's why we recommend the following management path in most cases:

Conclusion

As a dermatologist or family physician dealing with a skin lesion, we should leave the details to the pathologists. Either we are absolutely certain that a lesion is benign, or we should perform an excisional biopsy immediately for lesions <5 millimeters, or as soon as possible (within a maximum of 5 business days) for lesions >5 millimeters. The health benefits will be enormous.

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Conflicts of interest

The parent entity of LCG Greece Research has a working relationship with scanoma, a company for tele-dermatology.

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